

Holistic Development in Society

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ABSTRACT: Atomists believe that any whole can be divided and analyzed into its component parts, as well as from the perspective of the relationships between its components. On the other hand, the holists say that the whole is in fact much more than a sum of its parts. The atomist divides things to know them better, the holist approaches things or systems as an aggregate. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to understand more the nature and the essence of the systems as an aggregate.

KEY WORDS: holism, will, relations, whole, social, part

The holistic approach has grown in the 60–70s, where it leads to the emergence of more alternative systems in education, such as Montessori has replaced passive learning, based on memorizing with innovative learning and education methods. Montessori has proposed a specific, appropriate environment that contains useful materials that children are learning to learn at their own pace.

The Waldorf approach is based on the intuitive understanding of soul needs for each level of development. Quaker schools or neo-humanist education have adopted various concentration practices such as meditation, yoga, etc. The holistic term comes from the holistic meaning of the whole, and the medicine is the one that considers the being as whole. Co nduita therapeutic decided depending on a variety of issues that define the human being in a certain context.

Brian Fay asserted that holism has proven to be an arthritis for social science in two ways:

- a) Generally, science does not focus on individualism, but on classes of entities, especially on similarity;
- b) science does not want to describe than what he is studying, especially explaining and discovering causal forces

Belief in social holism can be seen as a product of tradition, having as authors Vico, Rousseau, Herder, but especially Hegel. The general principle of holism was expressed by Aristotle in *Metaphysics*, where the whole represents the sum of the parts right holistic conception, the integrity of beings can not be reduced to a mere sum of the constituent parts. This completeness it would be due to the action of an impenetrable, intangible force. The founder of holism was John Christean Smuts (1870–1950) through *Holism and Evolution*.

The notion of system is related to the structure (gestalt), where the psychological conception W. Kohler, K. Kaffka, K. Lerwin considers that psychic phenomena represent structures, integrated configurations, structures being primordial, irreducible realities, or partial processes subordinated to the whole. Gestalism is also called structuralism, configurationism, or form psychology. The structure designates how to create a system, an abstract model that expresses its functional scheme and the principles that underpin its internal cohesion.

The structuralist concept is used in the social field by CL Strauss, who explained the complex social structures through their dual, contractitor organization. As for the relationship between the party and the whole, holism has supported the primacy of the whole face. From the epistemological point of view, cultural studies aim at reconciling the two types of knowledge: cultural and objective. From this point of view, cultural studies are used by comparison as a means of revealing, by appealing to a holistic vision by observing and subduing the true nature.

For Aristotle, the first philosophy is in relation to philosophy in general, what arithmetic is in relation to mathematics. The first philosophy appears as part of the science of being as a finite. This

relationship between part and whole appears in the Aristotelian classification of contemplative sciences, where the first philosophy is seen as the second philosophy, namely physics.

Pierre Aubenque states that theology maintains with the other sciences a double relation of overlap and superiority; it is seen as a first philosophy, but different from the second philosophy. In the *Heavenly Aristotle*, Aristotle, after demonstrating the uniqueness of heaven with physical arguments, adds the same result that he could get arguments extracted from the first philosophy. In the *Treatise on Animal Movement*, Aristotle reminds that all inorganic bodies are moved by other bodies.

Some think that potency only exists when it manifests itself in act, and the innate is acquired through habit, such as flute singing. Aristotle states that the act of good is better and more worthy than potency and gives us the example of a man we can say he is healthy, but also the fact that he may be sick, that is why there are the opposite: health and illness, rest and movement etc.

If we admit that things in the sensitive world are numbers, like harmony of music, then there must be a unity between them. The entire Aristotelian tradition as well as the Greco-Latin neoplatonism provided an explanation for the different types of reporting of one to the multiple. The idea that the world is eternal appears in the texts of Tempier as follows:

- (1) the nature of the species trains the eternity of the individual
- (2) the form's eternity is correlated with the eternity of matter
- (3) the world's eternity is consistent with the immutability of the divine will
- (4) The created intellect gives the world eternity

In Boethius's *Treatise*, we meet seven reasons why it is worth asking the question of the eternity of the world:

- (1) It is necessary to save the sentence of philosophy
- (2) This sentence does not contradict the Christian one
- (3) He supports the demonstrations, so he has the claims of a relative foundation
- (4) Faith is based on miracles

- (5) Conclusion of reason is science, different from faith
- (6) Some arguments are false
- (7) philosophy and faith are not contagious about the world's eternity

Alexander Baumgarten considers that there are several arguments from the perspective of the creature, some from the creator's perspective, but also the relationship between them.

- (a) Arguments from the perspective of the creature address the problem of the infinite and temporal structure, but also of the act and potency
- (b) the arguments from the creator's perspective lead to the following idea: although God is unchangeable, yet his creation is his own will
- (c) The arguments from the perspective of the report bring the world's cohesion

Types of arguments disputed by Albert the Great, St. Thomas and Singer in Brabant:

- (1) Arguments of the Substance—Concerning the Answer to the Question What is it? The problem of the first act, but also the uniqueness of the substantial form
- (2) Hierarchy Arrays: The neoplatonic ontological hierarchy assumes that the intelligent One and Multiple Intermediate—the cosmological messiah has as intercessor between the world and God the sky
- (3) Arguments of the intelligent—who diversifies our knowledge, there is a different representation, a different intelligible species
- (4) The omnipotent argument of the theme of the divine lime—can God do a naval order?

If we compare these arguments, we observe that the first three are limits of the Aristotelian paradigm, philosophical principles, where the most important principle is that all reality becomes itself by its own act. Singer of Brabant did not apply this principle, considering that the unique intellect is a reality that does not become private by its

activity. From these polemics of the unit of intellect, five conclusions result:

- (1) Aristotel states that there are a number of explanatory systems; this category includes the idea of the pure potency of the intellect, the analogy between the soul and the sky, the analogy between the intellect and the whole nature
- (2) The theme of the receptacol limit of reality, the theme approached by Albert the Great
- (3) The problem of the intelligible sky—the theory of the unit of intellect and the thesis of the world
- (4) For the aristotel the soul is eternal and individual
- (5) philosophy invokes the theme of a given individuality

The concept of the philosophical paradigm designated the group of propositions that provided the arguments of authority that substantiated the disputes:

- (1) Circularity of heaven provides eternity to the world
- (2) Intelligent Heaven contains all universal species
- (3) suflet is the cause of time
- (4) suflet and nature know analogous principles
- (5) the intellect is indeterminate

In the Platonic–Aristotelian tradition of the 13th century, the sky was working, that is, the idea that heaven is a sensible and intelligible reality with three fundamental properties:

- (1) Subdued of sensitive things
- (2) Analogous to the soul
- (3) Intermediate between the world and the absolute transcendent

T. Herseni distinguishes three significant moments of the social structure of the will:

- (1) Psychic Will—pushing individual will to social one takes place due to sympathy, friendship; (Herseni affirms that defense, escape, struggle, defense, in fact, instincts are gained

from an effort to adapt to the environment and maintain the organic link between the individual and the social psychic will.)
(2) The Will Structure—involves the functioning mechanisms of the will in order to obtain a goal;
(3) The Life in Society—the participation of man in social life, actually identifying man with his needs.

Holists say that the whole is in fact much more than a sum of its parts. The atomist divides things to know them better, the holist approaches things or systems as an aggregate, and that is why we try to understand more their nature in essence.

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